

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE OF
POLY CYSTIC OVARIAN DISEASE AMONG GIRLS IN A
SELECTED COLLEGE AT KANCHEEPURAM DISTRICT,
TAMILNADU**

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Abstract:

A descriptive study to assess the knowledge of poly cystic ovarian disease among girls in a selected college at Kancheepuram District, Tamilnadu. 140 samples were selected by using convenience sampling technique. Self-administered questionnaires were used to assess the knowledge of poly cystic ovarian disease. The result showed that 0.71% of the girls had excellent knowledge 2.14% of the girls had very good knowledge, 0% of the girls had good knowledge, 13.57% of the girls had average knowledge, 83.7% of the girls had below average knowledge.

Key Words: Knowledge, Polycystic Ovarian Disease & Girls

Introduction:

Polycystic ovarian diseases (PCOD) is reported to be a growing problem with adolescent girls. It can be very difficult to diagnose. Polycystic ovarian diseases in teen age girls as they often experience irregular absent menses and acne. It is also known as stein eventual syndrome. Polycystic ovarian diseases about 6 to 10 percent of girls affected by this disease and even not aware of their presence. Polycystic ovarian disease prevalence is fast increasing among college girls, in urban about 30% college girls were detected with the poly cystic ovarian disease. Gynecological problems of adolescents occupy a special space in the spectrum of gynecological disorders of all ages. This is because of the physical nature of the problems which are so unique, special, and specific for the age group, and also because of the associated and psychological factors which are very important in the growth and psychological remodeling of someone in the transition between childhood and womanhood. Gynecological diseases are fairly common but most of us women ignore the symptoms or we are unaware, till the time the problem really worsens. One of them, now a days faced by girls, is Polycystic Ovarian Disease. This is the commonest course of Amenorrhea in young girls.

Significance of the Study:

According to an article published in the fertility Science and Research Journal of the Indian Fertility Society in 2014, 1 out of every 5 women in the reproductive age and as height as 2 out of every 5 adolescent in India are diagnosed with poly cystic ovarian diseases. A study on teen girls and college girls in several colleges around India was found to show a higher percentage of college girls with Polycystic ovarian disease and there was around 36% of increase in cases of Polycystic ovarian disease compared from a period of 2012 – 2013 showing a severe fast increased case of Polycystic ovarian disease among college girls in an alarming rate. Lakshminarayana, S [2014], conducted a study & found that, there were 259 girls in the sampling frame of which 238 gave their informed consent. Their age ranged from 17 to 25 years with a mean of 20.57 years body mass index was in 17-34. Although the diseases manifests even as an adolescent diagnosed of this condition has remains lagged. The prevalence of poly cystic ovarian diseases among young adult under graduated girls was 12.18% more than half of the cases remains undetected. The researcher had perceived the importance of the young women to be aware of this disease, and thus planned to conduct this study. PCOD affects 7 – 10% of women of childbearing age (15 to 45 years). In women of Indian subcontinent, prevalence rates as high as 50% have also been detected and is a leading cause of primary infertility secondary to an ovulation.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To assess the level of knowledge of polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD) among girls in a selected college at Kelambakkam, Kanchipuram dist Tamil Nadu.
- ✓ To associate between the level of knowledge on polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD) with the selected demographic variables among girls in a selected college at Kelambakkam, Kanchipuram District Tamil Nadu

Null Hypothesis:

H₀₁ –There is no significant association between the levels of knowledge of PCOD with selected demographic variables among girls in a selected college at Kelambakkam, Kanchipuram District Tamil Nadu

Methodology:

The researchers have used Descriptive research design using a quantitative approach
 Sample: 140 girls in a selected college who were selected by using convenience sampling technique
 Tool Used: self administered questionnaire
 Statistical Techniques Used: descriptive and inferential statistics used to analyze the data

Findings and Discussion:

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of knowledge of girls regarding poly cystic ovarian disease

S.No	Level of Knowledge	No of Sample	Percentage
1	Excellent	1	0.71%
2	Verygood	3	2.14%
3	Good	0	0%
4	Average	19	13.57%
5	Below Average	117	83.57%

Table 1 shows that 83.57% of girls had below average knowledge whereas 0.71% had excellent knowledge

Table 2: Association of demographic variables and the level of knowledge

S.No	Characteristics	Category	No. of Sample	Knowledge					X ²	P Value
				Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Below Average		
1	Age	17-20	98	1	1	0	16	80	6.87	9.49 (0.05) *NS
		20-23	42	1	0	2	12	37		
2	Socio Economic	Below Poverty	65	0	1	0	17	47	17.4	9.49 (0.05) Significant
		Under Poverty	75	1	2	0	2	70		
3	Qualification	Under graduate	107	0	0	0	19	88	8.36	9.49 (0.05) *NS
		Post graduate	33	0	3	0	0	30		
4	Year of education	1 st year	17	0	0	0	0	17	8.03	9.49 (0.05) *NS
		2 nd year	103	1	3	0	17	18		
		3 rd year	30	0	0	0	0	20		
5	Dietary pattern	Vegetarian	21	0	0	0	0	21	4.29	9.49 (0.05) *NS
		Non Vegetarian	119	1	3	0	17	98		

Table 2 show that demographic variable such as socioeconomic status had a significant association with the knowledge.

Conclusion:

This study helps us to understand that the need of awareness among the college girls regarding polycystic ovarian disease.

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